

Studies on Rhythmic Formations.

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Though rhythmic structures are usually produced in a suitable gel medium, the presence of a gel, however, is not indispensable. Numerous instances of rhythmic precipitations in the complete absence of a gel are known, as in the experiments of Runge ("Der Bildungstrieb der Stoffe," Oranienburg), Lenk and Brach (*Kolloid Z.*, 1911, 8, 325), Morse and Pierce (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1908, 45, 589), Dreaper (*Kolloid Z.*, 1914, 14, 163) and Holmes (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 40, 1187).

A remarkably well formed rhythmic precipitation of lead iodide, in the absence of any gel medium was obtained by Notboom (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 32, 247). A drop of a dilute solution of potassium iodide was placed on a glass plate, which was then covered with a microscope cover slip. On putting a drop of concentrated solution of lead nitrate round the edges of the cover slip, the precipitated lead iodide began to form in well separated layers. Similar periodic structures of silver chloride between two glass plates were also obtained by Brodersen (*Kolloid Z.*, 1924, 35, 21).

The fact that Liesegang structures can be grown in the total absence of any gel medium has actually been advanced by Notboom as a strong argument in favour of the Ostwald's supersaturation theory. In the following pages the formation of periodic precipitates in the complete absence of a gel has been studied in detail and it has been found that Notboom's conclusions in interpreting his experimental results in support of Ostwald's theory are not justified.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Two drops of reacting solutions were placed on a clean glass plate, and were separated from one another by a fine paraffin line. The drops were then covered with a similar glass plate, and the two advancing surfaces were just caused to meet by a slight movement of the top plate. At the junction of the two surfaces the precipitate began to form. The growth of the precipitate was followed by means

of a microscope which was fitted with a movable stage. A large number of precipitates were studied and in nearly every case distinctly periodic structures were obtained. Periodic precipitation was obtained with the following substances:—silver chromate, silver chloride, silver iodide, silver silicate, lead iodide, lead chromate, lead sulphide, barium carbonate, barium sulphate, barium oxalate, mercuric iodide, mercurous chloride, cadmium sulphide, manganese dioxide, ferric hydroxide, copper ferrocyanide and Prussian blue. In most of the above experiments a normal solution of one of the reacting substances was used against an $N/10$ —solution of the other. A few of the typical structures are shown in the accompanying microphotographs.

Discussion of Results.

Periodic precipitates between two glass plates have been obtained previously with only two substances, *vis.*, with lead iodide and silver chloride. In the present paper periodic precipitates have been obtained with about sixteen different substances which show clearly that the phenomenon is quite a general one. The precipitates obtained with the sulphides showed the characteristic property of Liesegang structure, namely the distance between the precipitate layers increased with increasing distance from the centre of diffusion as can be seen from the microphotograph of the lead sulphide structure.

The experiments of Hatschek and co-workers (*Kolloid Z.*, 1912, 10, 124), in which they were able to obtain rings of lead iodide in an agar gel already containing fine particles of lead iodide, have thrown the supersaturation theory in great doubt. It has however, been argued by Notboom that the experiments of Hatschek are inconclusive and do not disprove the supersaturation theory of Ostwald. In Hatschek's experiments the solid particles of lead iodide previously added to the gel, do not necessarily act as nuclei for releasing supersaturation as the particles have already undergone a process of adsorption, and are thus covered with a layer of the substance of the gel. In effect, the added particles of lead iodide act only as so many tiny masses of the gel and consequently possess no power of releasing supersaturation. So far as the author is aware, the above arguments of Notboom have not been satisfactorily met either by Hatschek or by any subsequent worker on the subject.

In a series of experiments the author has been able to obtain periodic precipitates of lead iodide, silver chromate and silver iodide in the presence of solid particles of the substances respectively and in the complete absence of any gel medium. Freshly precipitated lead iodide, silver chromate and silver iodide were carefully washed free from electrolytes, dried in a steam oven and finely powdered in an agate mortar. Drops of the reacting solutions were initially mixed with the finely powdered particles, placed on a glass plate separated by a fine paraffin line and were finally covered with a similar glass plate. In spite of the presence of the solid particles to act as nuclei, periodic precipitates of lead iodide, silver chromate and silver iodide were produced. Evidently then the periodic structures can be produced in the presence of solid particles uniformly distributed and in the complete absence of a gel. Notboom's arguments against the experiments of Hatschek are not applicable to the present experiments, as no gel medium, which could cover the surface of the particles by adsorption, is present. One is thus forced to the conclusion that supersaturation does not lie at the basis of any satisfactory explanation of the Liesegang phenomenon.

Brodersen (*loc. cit.*) made an ultramicroscopic examination of the precipitate formed between two glass surfaces during the course of its formation. He found that the precipitate at one stage was fine enough to show distinct Brownian movement. Notboom, however, failed to record any such movement. I have repeated the experiments of Brodersen with a large number of precipitates including lead iodide and have found that in every case the precipitate at the early stages of its formation appears as tiny particles which show very marked Brownian movements.

The experiments of Dreaper (*loc. cit.*) and of Brodersen (*loc. cit.*) show that the dimensions of the capillary spaces exert a great influence on the nature of the structures formed. This is so because on its magnitude depends the rate at which the two reacting solutions diffuse into one another. Another important factor affecting diffusion is the concentration of the reagents and in all experiments on ring-formations the use of a concentrated solution of one reagent with a weak solution of the other is well-known. It thus seems that ionic diffusion is mainly responsible for the phenomenon and accordingly the following tentative explanation for the formation of periodic precipitates in the absence of a gel is suggested.

Let us consider the case of a normal solution of lead nitrate diffusing into the thin film of an $N/10$ —solution of potassium iodide enclosed between two glass plates. As soon as the two films meet, a line of precipitates is formed and if now we confine ourselves to a small section of the potassium iodide film immediately on the border line of this precipitate, we find that the depletion of iodide ions in this region, in any time t , is due to—

- (i) Natural diffusion of iodide ions towards the lead iodide precipitate layer which is of zero iodide ion concentration;
- (ii) Removal as lead iodide by the fast arriving lead ions. The supply of iodide ions on the other hand is due to the diffusion of the $N/10$ -potassium iodide against a concentration of potassium iodide which is gradually falling from $N/10$ downwards.

It is thus apparent that this section is being impoverished of iodide ions much faster than the supply and one may therefore reasonably assume that when t is small the contraction of iodide ions in this region falls so low as not to form any precipitate with the fast approaching diffusion wave of lead nitrate, which sweeps over this region leaving a gap and forms another layer of precipitate a little ahead. This process repeats itself and thus we get finally a series of stratified rings or layers.

The effect of using a weaker solution of potassium iodide will be to diminish the supply of iodide ions still more with the result that the region depleted of iodine ions will be wider. It has actually been observed that the gaps obtained with $N/100$ -potassium iodide are much wide than the ones with $N/10$ -potassium iodide solution. This also explains the gradual widening of the gaps towards the end in a typical Liesegang structure of lead iodide as the concentration of potassium iodide continuously falls.

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Ag_2CrO_4 in presence of particles.

Ag_2CrO_4 .

PbS .

AgI .

Ag_2SiO_3 .

MnO_2 .

